

Data on zinc deficiency symptoms.^a Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	% of leaves affected		Intensity of leaf area affected (%)	
	AV	TV	AV	TV
Control	67.3	55.1	31.2	34.0
Azolla 10 t/ha	42.0	40.4	12.3	20.5
" 20 "	17.5	24.7	5.9	14.1
" 30 "	8.7	17.2	2.0	8.1
" 40 "	3.1	10.1	0.7	4.8
" 50 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 60 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 70 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 80 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 90 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 100 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
C.D. (P= 0.05%)		6.3	4.7	

^aAV = actual value of zinc deficiency worked out in percentage; TV = transformed value (angular value) of the percentage of zinc deficiency. Intensity of leaf areas affected = the area of the leaf covered by zinc deficiency symptoms.

deficiency symptom on the 25th DT for each treatment was recorded (see table).

Significant reduction in zinc deficiency was observed with azolla application from 10 t/ha onward compared to the untreated control. The deficiency

symptom was negligible at 40 t azolla/ ha and the crop was completely free from it at 50 t/ha and above. ■

Comparison of supergranules, sulfur-coated and ordinary urea in transplanted Jaya rice

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A field experiment compared the effectiveness of urea supergranules, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and ordinary urea at low to moderate levels of nitrogen application (see table). At 30 kg N/ ha, the supergranules proved significantly superior to the best split of ordinary urea but statistically at par with SCU. At higher levels of nitrogen application (60 and 90 kg N/ha), supergranules and SCU were not superior to the best split, but were definitely superior to single basal incorporation. ■

Effects of urea supergranules, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and ordinary urea on transplanted Jaya rice, Pantnagar, India, 1980 rainy season.^a

Nitrogen rate (kgN/ha)	Source and method of application ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	No nitrogen	2.5
30	Urea, best split	3.6
30	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.1
30	Supergranules of urea, placed ^a 10-12 cm deep	4.3
60	Urea, best split	5.2
60	Urea, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.2
60	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	5.1
60	Supergranules of urea, placed 10-12 cm deep	5.3
90	Urea, best split	5.8
90	Urea, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.3
90	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	5.7
90	Supergranules of urea, placed 10-12 cm deep	5.7
		S.Em. ± 220
		C.D. (5%) 640
		C.V.(%) 9

^aNursery sowing: June. ^bPlacement was in the center of 4 hills.

Environment and its influence

A simple screening technique to identify rice genotypes with low photorespiration

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C₃ and C₄ plants are known to differ sharply in their response to physical factors such as light, temperature, and oxygen concentration. Physical conditions largely govern the efficiency of the physiological and biochemical parameters that control the growth processes. Adverse physical stresses such as high temperature, light intensity, or oxygen concentration enhance photorespiration and impose a premium on net photosynthetic efficiency for productivity in C₃ plants.

Gangadharan and Kleinhofs have used those stress parameters in a screen-

ing technique to isolate barley and wheat genotypes that are more efficient in net photosynthesis. Only the two stress parameters oxygen and light are now used for rice.

A plexiglass chamber, 1.5 × 0.6 × 0.6 m was placed on a zinc tray filled with water, with outlet and inlet. A measured quantity of oxygen was let in daily for about 10 minutes through a flowmeter at 2 liters/ minute from an oxygen cylinder after the chamber was filled with atmospheric air so that the enriched air had an oxygen concentration of 25-26%. A mercury light continuously lighted the chamber at night to give a light intensity of 25-26 klux. A thermometer held through the ceiling of the chamber recorded temperature. Earthen pots, 10 cm in diameter, with 10 seedlings (aged 15-20 days) each, were kept on the tray in water. Four pots of maize seedlings were also dis-

tributed as checks for screening.

The seedlings turned pale and chlorotic after about 10 days and withered completely within 4 weeks. Some plants survived comparatively longer than others under high oxygen concentration. Data on seedling survival and photosynthetic rates after flowering and 3 days after oxygen enrichment in the chamber are in the table. Two runs were made on sets showing survival.

The preliminary observations clearly established variations in the rice genotypes' ability to withstand higher oxygen concentration under continuous light. These observations are relevant in that higher levels of oxygen inhibit the activity of the carboxylating enzyme (RuDP-carboxylase) and enhance RuDP oxygenase activity. Obviously photorespiration was enhanced under high oxygen levels. Genotypes with low oxygenase activity even at high oxygen level

Seedling survival and photosynthetic rate of different genotypes. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Genotype	Survival rate ^a (no. seedlings/pot)		Photosynthetic rate at flowering (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)	Photosynthetic rate at 3 days after O ₂ enrichment (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)
	Run I	Run II		
IET 4087	3/4		28.67	8.36
4105	—		12.01	4.19
5631	—		15.66	5.27
3852	—		14.44	5.62
5882	4/3		29.30	8.25
5887	—		21.14	7.15
5890	—		18.28	6.10
5897	—		16.30	4.19
6145	3/3		27.14	9.12
6205	—		17.21	6.15
6207	5/4		25.42	8.37
6208	—		17.25	4.15
6209	3/4		24.24	7.92
6212	—		14.16	4.12
6271	—		18.47	5.13
6658	4/4		27.12	8.67
5606	3/3		34.83	9.15
2812	—		13.28	4.19
Jagannath	4/5		23.71	7.67
Pankaj	3/4		18.17	4.89
Intan	—		13.60	4.14
RPW4-14	—		21.39	7.12
Vijaya	5/4		29.58	8.36
T141	5/5		26.22	8.65
CR 1014	—		15.23	7.18
IR8	4/5		25.16	8.91

^a — = nil survival. Total number of seedlings/pot = 10.

survived better because their photorespiration rate was lower and their net photosynthetic efficiency was greater.

This technique helps in rapidly identifying promising rice cultivars that are efficient in photosynthesis. It is easier to

use and less cumbersome than the low carbon dioxide concentration techniques normally used to identify photosynthetically efficient plants. Large-scale screening is tried at CRRI and results are being confirmed. ■

Morphological evidence of air passages between culms and roots in rice

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The mechanism of oxygen transport from shoot to root in the rice plant has been assumed to be associated with the passive diffusion of air through air passages in the tissue. If this view is correct, then it is important that such an air passage, which would allow the free transport of air from the top of the plant to the roots, be demonstrated.

Numerous studies have shown that lysigenous spaces and aerenchyma intercellular spaces are present in the cortical tissues of the rice plant culm. Similar lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces

are also present in the roots. The literature shows that these lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces may be responsible for the passive transport of air in the plant. But what is not certain is whether the lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces in the culm are connected in any way with the lysigenous and aerenchymatous spaces of the root.

A longitudinal section cut through the junction point between the culm and the root (Fig. 1) shows that between the cortex and the central vascular tissues of the culm there is a band of sclerenchymatous tissue, about 0.1 mm thick (Fig. 2). This thick layer of sclerenchymatous tissue could act as a barrier, if not totally stop, the passive flow of air between shoot and root.

To see if this layer of sclerenchymatous tissue would act as a barrier to the

1. The outer appearance of the rice plant (variety IR36) at the junction point between the root (R) and the culm. L = leaf sheath.

2. A longitudinal view of the rice plant at the junction point between the culm (C) and the root (R). Arrow indicates the position of the layer of the sclerenchymatous tissue.

3. Longitudinal section through the junction point between the culm and the root (R). Note that the continuity of the layer of the sclerenchymatous tissue (S) has been interrupted (arrow) by the aerenchymatous tissue (A). ×100.

4. Another view of the region similar to that shown in Figure 3. Note that in addition to the aerenchymatous tissue (A), the vascular tissue (V) also passes through the interrupted region (arrow). S = sclerenchymatous tissue. × 100.